

Install and use Rodin

Engineering

Exported on 03/16/2020

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https://sourceforge.net/projects/rodin-b-sharp/files/Core_Rodin_Platform/3.4/

Download

Download and run rodin

```
tar xvf workspaces/rodin-3.4.0.201802230927-6980ca1-linux.gtk.x86_64.tar.gz
cd rodin
sudo apt-get -y install openjdk-8-jdk
./rodin
```

Once running keep defaults

1 Install plugins

Help → Install new software

Click the dropdown arrow and select Atelier B Provers

Select Atelier B Provers

Next → Accept terms → Finish

Install progress in bottom right and will restart when done

Repeat for Rodin → Modelling Extensions → Event-B Theory Feature

Repeat for ProB → [ProB for Rodlin3 & ProB for Rodine - EXPERIMENTAL (Dis)Prover]

2 Import project

File → Import

General Existing projects in workspace (Next)

Select Archive file (/home/vagrant/workspaces/Rodin/MathExtensions.zip)

Finish

Repeat for /home/vagrant/workspaces/Rodin/SwiftAid_Candidate_1.zip

Set totalTickTocks = 6

Set advanceAuthzPeriod = 3

```

o totalTickTocks >
o embargoPeriod >
o maxYearCount >
o advanceAuthzPeriod >
AXIOMS
o axm1: totalTickTocks ∈ 1..365 not theorem >
o axm2: totalTickTocks>0 not theorem >
o axm3: totalTickTocks = 6 not theorem >
o axm4: embargoPeriod ∈ N not theorem >
o axm5: embargoPeriod = 1 not theorem >
o axm6: maxYearCount ∈ N not theorem >
o axm7: maxYearCount = 2 not theorem >
o axm8: advanceAuthzPeriod>0 not theorem >
o axm9: advanceAuthzPeriod=3 not theorem >
END

```

Window → Perspective → Open Perspective → Other...

ProB (Open)

Move between ProB and Rodin EventB top right buttons.

In EventB, Right click Machine and select Start Animation / Model Checking (Ignore warnings)

Click SETUP_CONTEXT

click INITILISATION

Restart Animation

